

THE ASSESSMENT OF BUILDER'S ROLE IN ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE BUILDINGS IN NIGERIAN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY.

CASE STUDY (LAGOS STATE)

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable buildings in built environment require that the use of resources such as energy, water, and unwanted outputs such as greenhouse gases are minimized whilst maximizing the health and wellbeing of users and so as to mitigate the environmental impact of buildings. There is need for sustainable building practice in Nigeria as buildings generally show signs of poor design for ventilation, natural lighting, energy management, water management, waste management and other building services. Hence the aim of this research is to evaluate the perception of builders in relation to their competence in achieving sustainable buildings in Lagos state, Nigeria. Data were obtained using 90 copies of a structured questionnaire, administered through a random sampling technique to builders in Lagos state while the considered builders has been registered under NIOB or CORBON with sufficient experience in building projects and 63 questionnaires was retrieved. The methods of data analysis were simple percentage, mean score, RII (Relative importance index). The findings of the research assess 10 specific roles of a builder was identified in the attainment of sustainable buildings. The average mean score of 4.32 indicates that the overall level of competence is moderate. This study also recommends that builders should be well acquainted with the roles they should play in main-streaming sustainability and considerations for builder's involvement at the design stage and the demand for best buildings practices by government and professional practices. Finally the study highly recommends sustainable building be encouraged at all cost in Nigeria.

Keywords: Sustainability, Builders, Sustainable building, Lagos state, Nigeria

1.0

INTRODUCTION

As human modernization increases the construction industry has been one of the industries contributing to environmental threats by taking up large amount of energy, non-renewable resources particularly fresh water, timber and lime stone which contributes to natural resources' depletion as well as being responsible for high levels of pollution, climate fluctuations and variations and other environmental threats such as destruction causing destruction of the ecosystem, desertification, and soil erosion, and increasing material wastage ,air and water pollution, deforestation, health hazards, global warming, and other negative consequences (Saroop and Allopi, 2014).

Suliman and Abdelnaser (2009) observed that construction accounts for an estimated 40% of all resources consumption and produces about 40% of all wastes, including greenhouse gas emissions. The construction industry has a role to play in ensuring a healthy livable environment and equitable access to social infrastructure and sustainable development in developing countries (Kheni and Akoogo, 2015). Berardi (2011), explained that a sustainable building is a building that preserves and maximizes functionality and serviceability, it is designed to maximize aesthetic quality and life-cycle cost. It is a building designed to achieve the purpose for its use with minimum environmental impact. A sustainable building should target being resource efficient, energy efficient (including greenhouse gas emissions reduction), pollution preventive (including indoor air quality and noise abatement), and environmental friendly.

A professional builder is trained to various fields of knowledge associated and related to building construction, operation and maintenance. The Builder's role can be styled into various ways such as acting as a maintenance management, facility management, construction management, contracting and services of a building etc, to achieve various purposes in order to ascertain sustainability in a building's life cycle (Dania *et al.*, 2013).

Waziri *et al.* (2015) stated that the level of sustainability practices' adoption in Nigeria falls below the international standard with very scanty studies in particular. Other professionals like architect, engineers (mechanical and electrical), structural engineers, quantity surveyor etc. spend limited time in the life-cycle of the building by starting their role at the design stage and ending it at the construction stage. A builder as a well trained professional has is capable of playing his role in

either the design, construction or maintenance stage of a building depending on the contractual involvement.

Design–build methodologies offers a process for increased builder (contractor) involvement throughout the project life cycle, allowing builder or general contractors to better manage increased role, including achieving sustainable objectives, which are often coupled with alternative project delivery. Whether builders view this as a positive opportunity to affect the sustainability of projects, and have taken advantage of it, has yet to be seen. The builders or contractors potential to influence the sustainability of project outcomes could lead to significant sustainability improvements in the Nigerian construction industry, including reduced greenhouse gas impacts of the built environment.

In conclusion this research aims to establish the roles builders' needs to play to achieve sustainability in buildings in Nigerian context.

2.0 THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENT FOR THE STUDY

2.1 Sustainable building

Berardi (2011), defined sustainable building as a building that preserves and maximizes functionality and serviceability. It is designed to maximize aesthetic quality and life-cycle cost. When a building is designed to achieve the purpose for its use with minimum environmental impact, it will contribute to achieving sustainable building (Feige *et al.*, 2013). With reference to OECD (2003), a sustainable building should target being resource efficient, energy efficient (including greenhouse gas emissions reduction), pollution preventive (including indoor air quality and noise abatement), and environmental friendly.

Few authors (Cassidy, 2003; Lowe, 2007; EPA, 2008) have also considered a sustainable building to be one that has high efficiency in the use of energy, water and materials, and also reduced impacts on health and the environment in terms of reduced greenhouse gas emissions throughout its life-cycle. This view is supported by Palanivelraja and Manirathinem (2010) who state that sustainable buildings are buildings that use resources such as energy, water, materials, and land more efficiently, with more natural light and better air quality so that these buildings contribute to improved health, comfort and productivity. It can be seen again from the descriptions above that a

sustainable building is related to the sustainable development agenda in terms of the environmental, social and economic aspect.

Major constituents of sustainable building

2.1.1 Waste management

Waste includes extracting, processing, using and discarding of raw materials in order to meet human needs. However, after man has made use of what seems to be beneficial to him, the remaining is discarded as waste. In relation to the SD agenda, the world can no longer afford to lose more resources to waste and particularly in the light of the depleting non-renewable resources (Mavropoulos, 2015). Therefore, in order for the construction industry to meet up with sustainable development, waste management is introduced as criteria for the development of sustainable buildings. Waste occurs both at construction stage, operations and the demolition stages of the build life-cycle and is a major contributor to environmental pollution (Dania *et al.*, 2015).

2.1.2 Pollution

The reduction of carbon emissions in buildings is related to greenhouse gas emissions which are the result of burning fossil for energy availability. Significant greenhouse gas emissions are also generated at the construction stage through construction materials, and in particular insulation materials, refrigeration and cooling systems (Vanags and Mote, 2011). The use of equipment that makes use of diesel and oil and chemicals such as paint, solvents and cleaners is major source of carbon emission. The infiltration of these substances into the soil and water disturbs plant and aquatic life (Vanags and Mote, 2011).

2.1.3 Maintenance

There are many definitions of maintenance, however, BS 3811 (1984, pp.1) defines it as '*the combination of all technical and administrative work including supervision, intended to retain an item, or restore it, to a state in which it can perform a required function*'. In relating maintenance to buildings, the CIOB (2004) describes building maintenance as the work carried out to preserve, renovate or improve every part of a building, its services and surroundings to a particular standard, determined by the balance between the need presented and available resources. BREEAM-NC (2012) states that maintenance of a building involves life-cycle costing and service life planning in order to inform decisions relating to design, specification and through-life maintenance and operation.

2.1.4 Sustainable Material

Sustainable material as a sustainable building constituent involves responsibly sourced materials, construction materials with low environmental impact and constructed in an environmentally sound manner in terms of resource use. The building industry is a major contributor to the global economy; however as earlier mentioned it is one of the main contributors in resource consumption and waste production, playing a fundamental role in sustainable development. This pushes the industry to design buildings built with minimum consumption of materials (Cobîrzan *et al*, 2013).

2.1.5 Indoor air quality

With reference to Billie (2012), the indoor environment is where people spend most of their time and it is widely accepted that it is important for health and wellbeing. The indoor environment provides a high level of protection against adverse health effects caused by extreme weather. Indoor air quality as a sustainable building constituent refers to the quality of a building's internal environment in relation to the health and wellbeing of occupants.

2.2 BUILDER'S ROLE IN RELATION TO THEIR COMPETENCE IN ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE BUILDING

A Builder is empowered to be the contractor or stand as a consultant to plan, monitor and supervise the running of numbers of different project. However according to the Associated General Contractors of America (2007), contractors are important for the success of sustainable or green projects, here this depicts the builder acting as a contractor. Some contractors may be involved in the design process; however, builders' involvement in implementing a project is often limited by the project-delivery system and the contract specifications. The Association further stresses that builders can add expertise if they are included in the design process. Among others, the builder (contractor's) role on a green or sustainable project can be to:

1. Recycle and re-use construction and demolition debris;
2. Limit the use of hazardous materials on the jobsite;
3. Protect existing vegetation, donate cleared trees or mulch for use on site;
4. Make environmentally friendly purchasing decisions, and
5. Procure and install more energy-efficient mechanical and electrical systems.

However, Braganca (2007) indicates that designers and builders tend to favor straightforward solutions. Despite the fact that construction has contributed to global environmental problems

(Kennedy *et al.*, 2002), buildings are still being erected without taking the climatic consequences into account. This can possibly be attributed to a lack of knowledge or secondly, to satisfy the main human needs; people prefer simple and cheaper buildings.

Delivery methods and projects that allow for contractor involvement and feedback earlier in the delivery process generally were mentioned by the respondents as providing an increased opportunity for the contractor's ability to influence the sustainability of the project.

Korkmaz *et al.* (2010) conducted a survey to determine a set of metrics that can be used to evaluate high-performance sustainable building projects, ranging from contract structure to owner's attitude about sustainable building projects. Tan *et al.* (2011) extend the work of evaluating sustainable project delivery and discuss the role of sustainable construction practices in increasing a contractor's competitiveness in the marketplace. That work focuses on those practices entirely within the builder's purview, e.g., waste management on site, while his research seeks contractors' opinions on their competitiveness due to implementing sustainability more holistically on a project through collaboration with the design and owner teams.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research methodology, consideration will be given to the study population which refers to a group or objects to be studied. Also, the sample frame and the sample size which is always determined from the sample frame, sampling technique which is a method of selecting objects from the sample. The method of data collection is the tool which will be adopted to gather data from various respondents in selected in the sample. After the data has been collected, it needs to be analyzed using various statistical tools

3.3 Study population

Study population refers to the total number of items or objects in the set. The study population for this study includes all Registered Builders in Lagos state, Nigeria.

3.4 Sampling frame

The sampling frame for data collection in this study was limited to only builders in construction firms in Lagos state that are registered.

State	builders
Lagos	800

Source: NIOB (Lagos chapter 2019)

3.5 Sampling size

Israel, (1992) stated that the factors that influence sample size include: the purpose of the study, population size, the risk of selecting a "bad" sample, and the allowable sampling error. For this study, the sample size was analyzed using: Yamane's theory (1973)

$$n_o = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where n_o is the sample size,

e is the desired level of precision (90%) ie 10% acceptable error

N = Population

$$n_o = \frac{800}{1+800(0.1^2)} = 89 \sim 90 \text{ samples}$$

States	registered builders	sample size (n)
Lagos	800	90

3.6 Sampling technique

Sampling technique can be referred to as a method used in drawing samples from a population. For the purpose of this study, the sampling technique used was convenience sampling method. About - builders were selected at convenience due to some constraints.

3.7 Data collection instrument

The survey instrument for collection of data for this research work was through the use of a well-structured questionnaire administered to the respondents which includes: Builders in Lagos State Nigeria.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION

This section contains the results of the analysis of data collected for the study. It contains the descriptive results of the response rate of the questionnaires distributed to builders. This section also contains the results of evaluation of builders role in achieving sustainable building in Lagos state, Nigeria.

4.1 Data analysis interpretation

Ninety questionnaires (90) were administered to registered builders in Lagos who are still practicing, of which only a total of 63 questionnaires were retrieved successfully.

Details of Questionnaires Administered and Returned

Sample size	Questionnaire Distributed	Questionnaire retrieved	Percentage retrieved
90	90	63	70%

4.1.1 Demographic information of the builders

CATEGORY	CLASSIFICATION	NO	PERCENTAGE (%)
Professional registration to building	NIOB	40	63.5
	CORBON	16	25.4
	Others	7	11.1
	Total	63	100
Academic qualification	ND	2	3.2
	HND	8	12.7
	B. SC/ B. TECH	42	66.7
	M.SC /M.Tech	9	14.3
	PH.D	2	3.2
	Total	63	100
Years of working experience	0 - 5 years	32	50.8
	6 - 10years	12	19.05

11 - 15 years	11	17.46
16 - 20 years	5	7.94
More than 20	3	4.76
Total	63	100

Table 4.1 is a summary of background information of the respondents including; respective registration to building, academic qualification, type of respondent firm (either the one they work in or own), years of experience and number of buildings involved in over the years. A total of forty respondents filled that they are registered to NIOB and sixteen respondent filled that they are registered to CORBON, only seven respondent filled that they are registered to other body related to building while. The table also shows the academic qualification of the respondents; 3.2% are ND holder; 12.7% are HND holders; 66.7% had either B.Tech or B.Sc; 14.3% had either M.Tech or M.Sc while only 3.2% had Ph.D. the respondents years of experience were also analysed and it was discovered that 50.8% had 1-5 years of experience; 19.05% have experience of 6-10 years; 17.46% have worked between 11-15 years and only 7.94% have worked for 16-20 years and 4.76% worked for more than 20 years.

4.1.2 BUILDERS ROLE IN ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE BUILDINGS

Table 4.2: Responses to the role of builder in achieving sustainable building

Builders role	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	RII	Rank
Carry out maintenance of the building and services which ensures the durability and economic value.	63	4.62	0.551	0.924	1
Indulge in the use of sustainable materials in the construction of a building project	63	4.46	0.714	0.892	2

Advise on the development & execution of the periodic maintenance plan on the sustenance of the building.	63	4.46	0.692	0.892	2
Advise on an effective waste management system	63	4.44	0.642	0.888	3
Ensure use of sustainable materials in the replacement and maintenance of the building and services	63	4.29	0.682	0.858	4
Monitor and carries out activities that reduce waste of water during construction phase	63	4.29	0.658	0.858	4
Coordinate waste management during the construction of the building	63	4.29	0.705	0.858	4
Advise on the use of systems that reduce carbon emissions.	63	4.27	0.653	0.854	5
Help to provide a healthy indoor environment through advice and specification of designs that encourage ventilation.	63	4.25	0.595	0.85	6
Encourages on the use of renewable energy.	63	4.06	0.693	0.812	7

Table 4.2 shows the role of the builder's based on their competence in the goal of sustainability. It shows 'Carry out maintenance of the building and services which ensures the durability and economic value.' as the highest ranked role with a relative importance index of 0.924. This is followed by 'Indulge in the use of sustainable materials in the construction of a building project' (2nd ranked). The two highest ranked competences confirms the position that the builder is the main orchestral of construction process or execution of a building project. 'Advise on the

development & execution of the periodic maintenance plan on the sustenance of the building’ also ranked the 2nd highest ranked role but with lower standard deviation than the role before it. This supports that Builders are one of the key figure to aiding and supporting buildings towards environmental protection. *‘Encourages on the use of renewable energy’* ranked lowest with RII of 0.812, The results indicate that Builders whether of low, medium or high experience believe they are competent in all roles for achieving sustainable building in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study focuses on the assessment of builders’ role to achieving sustainable building in Nigeria, Lagos state as case study. This assessment reveals the following conclusion;

Findings from this research revealed that Builders have the competence to deliver sustainable buildings if they are involved right from the very beginning of the design process as they are conversant with building operations, maintenance and construction that affect the performance of the building.

Based on the conclusions drawn from this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Professional bodies such as NIOB and CORBON should enlighten members on the importance of sustainable practice and construction and organize trainings to facilitate the builders’ competence in sustainable buildings.
- ii. The role of the builder in sustainable buildings should be encouraged by stakeholders in the construction industry due to the builders’ competence in processes that contribute to a building’s sustainability at the design, construction and maintenance stages of the building life-cycle.
- iii. Development of legislation to promote the builder’s role in sustainable buildings and the government as a major employer of builders’ services will help promote the building profession as a promoter of sustainable development.

REFERENCES

- Abidin, N. Z. (2010). Investigating the awareness and application of sustainable construction concept by Malaysian developers. 34, 421–426.
- Abigo. A., Madgwick. D., Gidado. K. and Okonji.S. (2012).Embedding Sustainable Facilities Management in the Management of Public Buildings in Nigeria. EPPM 2012, University of Brighton, Brighton, UK,10-11September2012.
- Ahn, Y. H., Pearce, A. R., Wang, Y., & Wang, G. (2013). Drivers and barriers of sustainable design and construction: The perception of green building experience. *International Journal of Sustainable Building Technology and Urban Development*, 4, 1, 35-45.
- Akadiri, P. O. and Olomolaiye, P. O. (2012). Development of Sustainable Assessment Criteria for Building Materials Selection. *Eng. Constr. Archit. Management*, 19, 6, 666 – 687.
- Berardi, U. (2013). Clarifying the New Interpretations of the Concept of Sustainable Building. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 8, 72-78.
- CIB, Conseil International du Bâtiment. (2010). Towards Sustainable and Smart-Eco Buildings. Summary report on the EU-funded project smart-ECO buildings in the EU. Rotterdam: CIB.
- Dania, A. A. (2016). Sustainable Construction At the Firm Level : Case Studies From Nigeria. (May).
- Dahiru, D., A. A. Dania, A. A. and Adejoh, A. (2014). An Investigation into the Prospects of Green Building Practice in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 7, 6, 158 – 167.
- Daniel, E. I., Oshineye, O., & Oshodi, O. (2018). Barriers to sustainable construction practice in nigeria. (September), 149–158.
- Holloway, S., & Parrish, K. (2013). The contractor ' s self-perceived role in sustainable construction : survey. (July), 905–914.
- ISO Standard 21931 – 1. (2010). Sustainability in Building Construction –Framework for Methods of Assessment for Environmental Performance of Construction Works –Part 1: Buildings.
- Kheni, N. A. & Akoogo, M.A. (2015).Determinants of Sustainable Construction Practices in Ghana Using Structural Equation Modelling, *Journal of Sustainable Development*,8(3)67-78.

- Lancashire, C. (2017). Development of a Facilities Management Framework for Sustainable Building Practice in Nigeria By Olayinka Oluseyi Olaniyi. (July).
- Omorie, D., Alabi, O., & Emmanuel, A. (2018). Stakeholders' Perception of Sustainability in Educational Buildings in Nigeria. 9(1), 1–14.
- Otali, M. (2018). Evaluation of level of adoption of sustainability practices evaluation of level of adoption of sustainability practices among construction firms in the niger. (November).
- Saroop, S. H. & Allopi, D. (2014). Developing Eco Sensitive Infrastructure Solutions with the use of Sustainability Criteria, *International Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(2): 121-126.
- Sourani, A. (n.d.). A review of sustainability in construction and its dimensions. 536–547.
- Suliman, L. Kh. M. & Abdelnaser, O. (2009). Sustainable Development and Construction Industry in Malaysia, Economic, Social, Political and Cultural Problems of the Future Society.
- Vanags, J. and Mote, G. (2011). Sustainable Development in Construction: Conceptual Model and Latvia's Case Study. *Journal of Riga Technical University Economics and Business*, 21, 92-98.